

Comparative study between characteristics and metadata of preprint repositories

Monica Garcia

University of Coimbra, Faculty of Arts and Humanities, Coimbra, Portugal

monica.garcia@student.uc.pt

ORCID ID 0000-0003-0659-050X

Ana Lúcia Terra

University of Coimbra, CEIS20 - Center for interdisciplinary Studies, Coimbra, Portugal

anatterra@fl.uc.pt

ORCID id 0000-0003-1292-2849

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Abstract

The recent interest in preprints as a new way of communicating science and its acceptance by the scientific community has resulted in the growing number of preprint repositories, mainly due to the speed with which articles can reach researchers. Preprints are understood as manuscripts that have not yet been published in scientific journals, therefore, have not yet gone through the peer review process. The objective of this study is to compare the main characteristics and metadata of four preprint repositories - Arxiv, bioRxiv, EmeRI and SSRN. Through a qualitative approach methodology carried out in three stages: a bibliographic research, a web search of preprints repositories and the elaboration of a comparative table, it was verified that the analyzed repositories have policies and practices for the broadcast of preprints. In addition to offering metadata that influence the retrieval and access of information, as well as the preservation of indexed documents.

Keywords: arXiv , bioRxiv , EmeRI , SSRN, Preprints, Preprints repositories

Introduction

Over the past almost five centuries, countless changes have occurred in the process of communicating knowledge. Until the 17th century, inventions and discoveries were disseminated through letters, minutes, and even books and pamphlets. The minutes consisted of transcripts of the findings discussed at the meetings of the societies existing at the time, and were disseminated in printed format in a summarized way to the members of these societies (Stumpf, 1996, p. 1). In the 21st century, the dissemination of information reached a more significant number of researchers in different parts of the planet, in different formats and typologies, and almost instantly.

It is widely recognized that, in contemporary times, there is an acceleration of scientific dynamics. Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), as well as the Internet, facilitate the production and dissemination of scientific information. This condition has been amplified due to the pandemic of COVID-19, given the enormous effort to produce knowledge aimed at facing this health emergency. The pandemic seems to have drawn new perspectives on the science communication model. These new perspectives strengthen movements for free access to scientific information, and place researchers as one of the great disseminators of their own research results. In the search for an answer to this severe global public health crisis, the scientific community has been imprinting a new dynamic of knowledge production with substantial changes in the temporal perspective and in the articulation of networks. Researchers have been producing information at an accelerated rate: around 30,000 articles had been registered by the largest reference databases by the end of June 2020, with an average of more than 500 publications/day (Teixeira da Silva, 2020, p. 832) The genetic sequencing of the virus was achieved in record time, as was the production of the vaccine.

In a descriptive perspective, the objective of this study is to analyze how metadata are organized in different repositories of preprints and to verify how this structure influences the information retrieval. In this orientation, we seek to identify the main characteristics and policies adopted by the arXiv repositories; bioRxiv, SSRN and EmeRI. The choice of these repositories was because they are the main ones within their areas of knowledge (Li, 2015, p. 616; Packer, 2021, Príncipe, 2021, p. 67) and have specific characteristics that influence the dynamics of the organization of the information produced.

Study background

In the context of the Covid19 pandemic, preprint repositories gained prominence in the dissemination and access to research results, particularly due to the speed with which articles can reach researchers. Thus, one should consider the importance of investigating the knowledge organization strategy used by repositories, particularly from the perspective of information retrieval.

The need to speed up the dissemination of scientific information guided the creation of new formats, business models, access and dissemination of knowledge. In this sense, the preprint emerges as a new publication model. Preprints are manuscripts that have not yet been published in scientific journals, so they have not yet gone through the peer review process. Laporte (2017, p. 368) describes preprints as the circulation of articles among academics even before being published in a scientific journal. According to Tennant et al. (2018, p. 2) there is no clear consensus on the definition of preprints, and they emphasize the need to take into account their role in the modern publishing era and the specific differences of the

community. According to the authors, the definition of preprint must be linked to the lack of traditional peer review in academic journals, as this is important to the research community. They also propose differentiating preprint, postprint, Version of record (VOR) and e-print (Tennant et al. 2018, p. 2).

- Preprint: version of a research article, usually before peer review and publication in a journal;
- Postprint: version of a research paper after peer review and acceptance, but before any typography or text editing by the editor;
- Version of record (VCO): final published version of an academic research article after being formatted by the editor;
- E-print: version of a research paper posted on a public server, regardless of its peer review status, print publication, etc. Considers that the previous three are forms of e-print.

According to ASAPbio – Accelerating Science and Publication in biology¹, preprint is a scientific manuscript uploaded by the author to a public server.

The accelerated dissemination that the preprint provides translates into opportunities for researchers to share, almost instantly, their research with potential collaborators and demonstrate tangible evidence of achievement and productivity to interested funders and academic evaluators (Maggio, et al., 2018, p 287).

Preprint is not a recent publication model. In 1961, the National Institutes of Health (NIH), through an experiment called Information Exchange Groups (IEGs), reported preprints in biology. This program lasted until 1967 (Cobb, 2017, p. 3). In 1991, physicist Paul Ginsparg, of the Los Alamos National Laboratory, in the United States, launched the arXiv repository with the aim of disseminating free and open access scientific content within the area of high-energy physics (McKiernan, 2000, p. 128). New repositories were emerging in different areas of knowledge, as reported by the recent work developed by ASAPbio, which listed about 56 preprint platforms covering the areas of life sciences, biomedical and clinical services (<https://asapbio.org/preprint-servers>).

Preprint repositories are online platforms that allow free sharing of these manuscripts, they speed up the dissemination of research. According to Packer et al.:

The *preprints* are stored in a computational environment with a series of associated services, such as manuscript upload, acceptance or rejection controls, creation of new versions, comments, submission to journals, classification and presentation by subject, searches for different items, links, etc. The management and operation of the storage and associated services are called a *preprint* server or repository (Packer et al., 2017, p. 4).

Hyun and Seo (2019, p. 56) list some advantages of publishing in preprints repositories, such as:

- Allows rapid dissemination of results, as the preprint does not go through the processes required for publication in scientific journals;

¹ Created in 2016, ASAPbio is a non-profit organization that aims to encourage open and innovative communication in the life sciences. (<https://asapbio.org/preprint-info>).

- Preprint servers guarantee search priority when recording the publication upload date;
- Allows feedback by improving research before publication in a scientific journal; and
- Increases the possibility of being cited, as manuscripts receive DOI (Digital Object Identifier System) when they are posted.

As a tool for organizing and disseminating scientific production, preprint servers need to organize all scientific content/knowledge, establishing guiding policies for their operation. The policy must list the metadata used, establishing the description requirements for each element, as well as the forms of standardization and normalization, aiming at the syntactic and semantic quality (Torino, 2017, p. 105). Metadata represents not only a principle of organization but also a possibility for better information retrieval in guaranteeing access, sharing, reuse and preservation of documents. In fact, descriptive metadata is strategic for the knowledge organization (KO). Hjørland (2008, p. 86) describes that the KO, in its narrow meaning, is linked to the activities of description, indexing and classification of documents. It emphasizes that the KO, in the narrow purpose, needs to observe the knowledge in the broad sense, that is, to consider the organizational approach. Dahlberg (2006, p. 12) distinguishes KO between two actions: the construction of conceptual systems and the correlation or mapping of units of such concepts systems with objects of reality.

The journal *International Classification* (1974-1992) with a new nomenclature from 1993 onwards, *Knowledge Organization*, introduced Knowledge Organization as “the objects and activities of concept theory, classification and indexing and knowledge representation” (Dahlberg, 2006, p. 12). Here the representation of knowledge goes beyond a logical structure of the conceptual representation, but also issues related to the most appropriate terms and questions of terminology.

Metadata is defined, by the National Information Standard Organization (NISO), such as: “... this information we create, store, and share to describe things, allows us to interact with these things to obtain the knowledge we need” (NISO, 2017, p. 5). Demonstrating the complexity that today the definition of metadata requires attending to digital documents.

According to Sayão (2010, p. 5), corroborating other authors, metadata can be divided into three conceptual categories:

- Descriptive metadata: describe informational resources aimed at discovery and identification. They can contain elements such as the author, title, abstract, keyword and persistent identifier.
- Structural metadata: document as complex resources, made up of several components, should be recomposed and ordered. Such as, for example, linking and ordering separately digitized pages of a book;
- Administrative metadata: help the process of managing the life cycle of informational resources. This category includes the technical metadata that explain the specificities and technical dependencies of the resource and the metadata aimed at the management of rights related to the resources.

Metadata is grouped into structures known as schemas or metadata formats that, depending on the object to be described and the context, have a specific application. Machine Readable Cataloging (MARC) (<https://www.loc.gov/marc/umb/>) is a traditional scheme for library professionals. Other formats emerged with the advent of the web information system, such as Dublin Core (DC) (<https://dublincore.org>), Metadata

Object Description Standard (MODS) (<https://www.loc.gov/standards/mods/>), Learning Object Metadata (LOM) (https://pt.wikipedia.org/wiki/Learning_Object_Metadata), Metadata Encoding & Transmission Standard (METS) (<https://www.loc.gov/standards/mets/>), and others.

Methodology

This work presents a comparative study between four main repositories of preprints in their areas of knowledge. This study characterizes the repositories, identifies the metadata, as well as aims to identify similarities and differences between the descriptive representation metadata of the preprints. In order to achieve the objectives of this study, a qualitative approach methodology was chosen, carried out in three stages: a bibliographical search, a web search of the analyzed preprints repositories and an elaboration of a comparative table.

▪ *Bibliographic search*

It is important to point out that bibliographic search is a complement to the information found in the repositories, in order to add new information to the objectives, history and metadata of the repositories.

In this sense, the bibliographic search was initially carried out in international databases specialized in the information area: Library & Information Science Source (EBSCO), Scopus and Web of Science, on 19/01/2022.

In all these sources, the time frame of the publication of the works to be analyzed was taken into account. The search covered publications from 1990 onwards. This period was established as a result of the creation of arXiv in 1991.

In order to identify the Brazilian production on the subject, a search in the Reference Database of Journal Articles in Information Science – Brapci was carried out.

In order to rescue other productions that were eventually not indexed in the studied databases, searches were also carried out on Google Scholar.

In English, the descriptors used in the searches were the following: arXiv, bioRxiv, EmeRI, SSRN, Metadata, Preprints, and in Portuguese: arXiv, bioRxiv, EmeRI, SSRN, Metadata, and Preprint.

▪ *Web search of analyzed preprint repositories*

The second stage was carried out on the websites of the analyzed repositories, exploring information about the creation of the repositories, disciplinary scope, format used for manuscript submission, documents that are part of the policy and organization of the repositories, licensing options and descriptive metadata. The page about “Frequently Asked Questions” was significant, bringing information that contributed to the development of the work.

Results and discussion

Scientific knowledge often takes six months, a year or even longer to be published in a scientific journal, as articles go through the peer review system before being approved for publication. The emergence

of preprint repositories has brought changes in the way knowledge is communicated, not only in terms of speed of dissemination, but also in terms of greater visibility for the researcher by allowing feedback on their research, becoming better known, creating good partnerships or even attracting funders to their research search.

Through the survey carried out, it was possible to verify the main characteristics of the repositories initially studied, as described below.

- **arXiv.org** <https://arxiv.org/>

arXiv was created, in 1991, by particle physicist from the Los Alamos National Laboratory, in the United States, Paul Ginsparg to disseminate open and free content in the area of high-energy physics (McKiernan, 2000, p. 128). Today it is maintained and operated by Cornell Tech.

Initially, it was a project to organize a preprint random distribution in the field of high-energy physics. However, it quickly became an important tool for communicating ongoing research (McKiernan, 2004, p. 11). This immediate acceptance is due to technological advances and also to the pre-existing acceptance of preprints by the high-energy theoretical physics community (Ginsparg, 1994, p. 390).

McKiernan (2004, p. 11) believes that arXiv may have inspired the creation of other repositories or even other alternatives for academic publications.

Also in August 1991, 14 disciplines were added. Today, arXiv covers the following disciplinary scope: Physics, Mathematics, Computer Science, Quantitative Biology, Quantitative Finance, Statistics, Electrical Engineering and Systems Science and Economics.

Ginsparg (2016, p. 2621) highlights that one of the benefits for scientists to publish arXiv is the guarantee of claiming priority with date, recognized in the scientific community, giving automatic visibility to the author.

For submission, the author needs to register. There are no submission fees or costs, but all manuscripts go through a moderation process, which classifies material within a subject area, checks for scholarly value and is current (<https://arxiv.org/help/moderation>). All manuscripts receive DOI (Digital Object Identifier).

There is no peer review, and the author is entirely responsible for the content made available. According to Ginsparg (2016, p. 2624), the feedback received from readers brings contributions to improved versions of the article. Maggio (2018, p. 288), emphasizes that because there are readers from various origins, working with different philosophical positions and with different methods, feedback in preprint repositories contributes with new points of view and approaches.

In accordance with arXiv's governance principles, responsibility for the operation and development of the repository rests with Cornell University, with strategic and operational guidance from its Member Advisor (MAB) and its Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) (Ginsparg, 2016, p 2625).

Despite the speciality in the area of exact sciences, arXiv created a separate section on COVID-19 to facilitate the search and with access to medRxiv and [bioRxiv \(Link\)](#).

The repository provides usage statistics, making it possible to access the number of submissions received since August 1991. (<https://arxiv.org/stats/main>).

▪ **bioRxiv – The preprint server for Biology <https://www.biorxiv.org/>**

bioRxiv was launched, in 2013, by Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory (CSHL), a non-profit research institute. Its launch follows discussions with academic community members, arXiv and librarians (Server et al. 2019, p. 1).

The decision to name bioRxiv and not bio-aRxiv, following consultations with arXiv representatives, was concerned that users of bioRxiv might mistakenly contact the arXiv team for technical support for bioRxiv (Server et al. 2019, p. 2).

Articles do not undergo peer review. However, there is a check on offensive and/or non-scientific content, information that may cause harm to health or biosecurity, in addition to checking for plagiarism. Articles already published in scientific journals are not accepted.

All manuscripts receive DOI (Digital Object Identifier) and authors need to register to submit documents.

It is possible to find in the repository a list of scientific journals which receive transfer of manuscript files and metadata directly from bioRxiv.

In addition to monthly download statistics, bioRxiv also records whether a preprint was published elsewhere and in which journal (Abdill & Blekhman, 2019, p. 4).

The disciplinary scope includes Biology, Biochemistry, Bioengineering, Biophysics, Bioinformatics, Cancer biology, Cell biology, Developmental biology, Evolutionary biology, Plant biology, Synthetic biology, Systems biology, Scientific communication and education, Animal behavior and cognition, Ecology, Pharmacology and Toxicology, Physiology, Genetics, Genomics, Immunology, Microbiology, Neuroscience, Paleontology, Pathology and Zoology.

Papers on mathematics and physical sciences will only be accepted if relevant to the life sciences. The orientation is that preprints on these themes are sent to arXiv.

▪ **SSRN – Social Science Research Network <https://www.ssrn.com/index.cfm/en/>**

It arises with the aim of offering academics a way to publicize their research before publication in scientific journals, and undergo evaluation.

Founded, in 1994, by Social Science Electronic Publishing Inc., it has become an interdisciplinary service serving the social sciences, applied sciences, health sciences and physical sciences. In 2016, it was purchased by Elsevier, a multinational publishing conglomerate based in the Netherlands.

Publication is free; however, not all documents can be downloaded for free, most of them yes, with the exception of works whose copyrights are from third parties that request a download fee. It is partially open access and uses a different model from other repositories (Li et al. al., 2015, p. 617).

The user needs to register before publishing his work, and the documents receive the DOI. For health science case reports, there are additional requirements, the user needs to prove under patient trust and patient consent. Authors can withdraw their publications at any time, as SSRN does not claim copyright. Users grant a non-exclusive and revocable license (Ramsay, 2012, p. 136).

On the repository page, it is possible to find a classification of the main articles, authors and organizations, in addition to a section called “First Look”, where journals identify and make available content of interest before publication - preprints, accepted articles and articles under consideration. It is a partnership between the SSRN and some scientific journals to support the early dissemination of academic research in progress.

It is made up of more than 40 research networks in various areas of knowledge that aim to keep the researcher updated on research trends in the early stage – it is a paid subscription service.

On the site, it is also possible to access academic advertisements and job vacancies.

- **EmeRI–Emerging Research Information preprint repository, <https://preprints.ibict.br/>**

In May 2020, in times of a pandemic, Brazil launched the EmeRI repository, which emerged as a joint initiative between the Brazilian Association of Scientific Editors and the Brazilian Institute of Information in Science and Technology (Ibict), and has the partnership of the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (Unesco) to meet the need of some Brazilian scientific editors to accelerate the availability of articles submitted to their journals, mainly related to the coronavirus.

It was created within a context of support for the open access movement, open science, and thinking, in addition, to promoting the dissemination and expanding access to Brazilian scientific production, also accelerating the availability of scientific production submitted to Brazilian scientific journals (Amaro et al., 2020, p. 5).

Although the proposal is similar to that of other preprint repositories, that is, to provide access to scientific production before publication in journals, its functioning differs in that the insertion of preprints is done by the journals and not by the authors. All documents receive the DOI.

Journals from anywhere in the world can be indexed in EmeRI, they just need to agree with the pre-requisites defined in the informational policy.

As the deposit is made by the editors, there is already a preliminary evaluation of form and content carried out by specialists in their respective areas. This evaluation ensures that the preprint, even though it has not yet been evaluated, has already been accepted for the formal peer review process (Amaro et al., 2020, p. 6). EmeRI also has an International Ethics and Integrity Committee that reviews inappropriate content and may delete it.

As this is a repository in which the editor inserts the manuscript, feedback can occur in three situations, namely: in the event of a serious breach of ethics or scientific integrity being identified - it must be reported by email to the Committee International Ethics and Scientific Integrity of EmeRI; if there is an interest in acting as an official reviewer – in this case, the interested party must send an email to the editor of the journal expressing their interest; and, finally, if there are other comments or considerations regarding the content of the preprint – an email should be sent to the editor in Letter to the Editor format.

Two important documents are available on the repository page: the EmeRI Non-Exclusive Distribution License and Preliminary Review Statement and the Emerging Research Information (EmeRI) Information Policy.

Comparative analysis of the repositories

The metadata used in the repositories differs in some points due to the different characteristics of the repositories but they present also similarities [Table 1].

Table 1. Comparative table of metadata, type of documents, formats and licensing options for repositories (the authors, 2022)

REPOSITORY	arXiv	bioRxiv	emeri	SSRN
METADATA	Title, Author(s), Abstract, Comments, Report-no, Category, Journal-ref, DOI, MSC Class, ACM Class.	Title, Identifier, Date of publication/deposit, Name(s) of author(s), Affiliation(s) of author(s), Abstract, License type(s), Full – text content , References, Subject category.	Title, Abstract, Keywords, Author(s), Language, Editor(s) responsible for compliance review, Research data, Digital Object Identifier (DOI), Date of deposit, Bibliographic reference. MAGAZINE DATA: Title of the journal, ISSN, URL, Publishing institution, Country of publication of the journal, Areas of knowledge of the journal, Universal information services, Thematic information services.	Title, Identifier, Date of publication/dep osit, Name(s) of author(s), Abstract, References, Copyright permission (if applicable).
TYPE OF DOCUMENT ACCEPTED	research manuscripts	research manuscripts	research manuscripts	Various types (including research manuscripts, abstracts, editorials, opinion articles)
SUBMISSION FORMAT	(La)Tex, MAS(La) Tex, PDFLaTex, PDF, HTML with JPEG images, /PNG/GIF	PDF or individual text and figure files that undergo automated PDF conversion	PDF	PDF
LICENSING OPTIONS	Authors can choose between licenses: CC0, CC BY, CC BY-SA 4.0, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0, non-exclusive license for distribution, any other CC license as specified in the manuscript text; no preference for which license chosen.	Authors can choose between licenses: CC0, CC BY, CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND, CC BY-NC-ND or no reuse; no preference for which license chosen.	Crative Commons CCBY. However, all copyrights are reserved to the authors of the preprints.	Copyright is reserved to the authors.

EmeRI, for example, for its proposal to make available the articles sent to scientific journals, has in its metadata the information of the journals. arXiv has the MSC class which refers to the mathematical classification code according to the mathematics disciplines and the ACM class which indicates the classification code according to the “ACS Computing Classification System”. However, they all have fundamental descriptive metadata such as title, author, DOI and subject, to enable better information retrieval, guarantee access, sharing, reuse and preservation of indexed documents.

Despite not being on the arXiv metadata list, it must be said and as highlighted by Ginsparg (2016, p. 2621), one of the benefits of publishing in this repository is the guarantee of claiming priority with date. Hyun and Seo (2019, p. 56) reaffirm that one of the advantages of publishing in preprint repositories is precisely the guarantee of research priority at the time the publication upload date is registered.

The DOI, being a unique code for publications that are on the web, makes the file permanent on the web, guaranteeing the authenticity of the online publication. In addition to these benefits, according to Hyun and Seo (2019, p. 56), when receiving DOI, the manuscript can be cited in other academic publications immediately, having greater visibility.

However, it should be clarified that the preprint DOI is different from the ahead of print and the final version of a published article. Ahead of print has already passed peer review and has been accepted for publication. Before being published, they are made available online with DOI Crossref (Farley, 2018). According to the author, contents ahead of print share the DOI with their corresponding version of the record. The fundamental difference between preprints, ahead of print and registry versions is acceptance. It justifies, however, why preprints must have unique DOIs, while ahead of prints and record versions share a DOI.

DOI and publication date provide sustainability to the preprint, as it is a publication that has not yet undergone the traditional peer review, the type of evaluation characteristic of scientific journals.

Regarding the type of documents that can be submitted, almost all of them are research manuscripts, with the exception of the SSRN, which covers a broader range of documents, such as abstracts, editorials and opinion articles. SSRN works to share early-stage research, develop ideas, measure results, and connect students and faculty.

The default submission format for all repositories is PDF. Even though they accept individual text and picture files, they are converted to PDF, just like bioRxiv. However, arXiv accepts other formats, listing in order of priority. (La)Tex, MAS(La)Tex, PDFLaTex, PDF, HTML with JPEG/PNG/GIF images. They guide the choice of Tex/Latex because they consider this format to be highly portable and stable over time. Regarding the figures, they do not accept omitted figures, even if you send the link to view the figures externally.

Each platform has its own set of policies and practices regarding accepted documents, submission format and licensing. Of course, they all offer a copyright guarantee. The choice of license to use is very important, authors can apply an appropriate license depending on how they would like to share or reuse their work, allowing it to be translated, republished or used in other ways for free.

Conclusion

The recent interest in preprints as a new way of communicating science and its acceptance by the scientific community has resulted in a growing number of preprint repositories. These repositories have

specific features, such as manuscript upload, feedback, submission to scientific journals, classification and presentation by subject.

Its credibility is based on long-term sustainability, financial stability, maintenance, development, copyright guarantees and governance of preprint services.

The analyzed repositories have important policies and practices for the dissemination of preprints. On their web pages, they provide information policies and documents about their functionality and which assure the author about their copyright. In addition to offering metadata that influence the retrieval and access of information, as well as the preservation of indexed documents.

By analyzing preprint repositories, it is intended that this work can support researchers in selecting the best repository for accessing, retrieving and sharing scientific information.

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Disclosure statement

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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